

*Questions, Comments and Answers following the presentation*

*Calibrating the G-CLEF for Exoplanet Science*

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Mouillet:

1. *Fibre FoV?*
2. *In the future: if we considered monomode fibers, how would it change life for calibrations? (much easier, identical, unfeasible, completely different)?*

1. The fibers don't have a field of view in the classical sense - they are single object. However there is a range of fiber sizes which provide a range of resolution. The small fibers have a 0.7 arcsec acceptance angle (or seeing disk) and the largest fibers have 1.2 arcsecond acceptance.
2. Single mode fibers would be a boon, since they essentially erase all near and far field fluctuations. However, single mode fibers are small, so they have proved difficult to feed with good efficiency. There has been success, particularly by Bland-Hawthorn et al. with photonic lanterns that "dissect" multimode fibers into bundles of single mode fibers, thus have the coupling efficiency of multi-mode fibers and the immunity to output fluctuations that single mode fibers provide.

Roth: *Comment: There is an interesting variant of a tuneable laser that we have in fact already built and tested on sky: 4 wave mixing of two laser frequencies (one tuneable) in a non-linear fiber that creates a frequency comb with wide line spacing.*

Ramsay: *What are the key elements in the RV error budget that you are concentrating on at this stage of the design?*

For G-CLEF, my biggest present-day focus is providing high thermal, mechanical and optical stability. If we don't get that right during the design phase, improvements in technology and enhancements to technique will not have any effect.